

palimpsestR: An R Package for the Identification and Probabilistic Decomposition of Archaeological Palimpsests

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Abstract

This paper presents `palimpsestr`, an R package and Shiny application dedicated to the **identification and probabilistic decomposition** of archaeological palimpsests — deposits in which material from multiple occupation phases is superimposed and partially intermixed. Such deposits represent one of the most persistent analytical challenges in field archaeology, and existing tools (Harris Matrix recording systems, *k*-means spatial clustering, GIS overlays) typically address only one evidence domain at a time. `palimpsestr` implements the Stratigraphic Entanglement Field (SEF) framework, which integrates four evidence domains — horizontal coordinates, vertical elevation, chronological range, and cultural class — into a single diagonal-covariance Gaussian mixture model fitted by Expectation-Maximisation. The model is augmented with optional taphonomic weighting and stratigraphic entanglement penalties derived from the Harris Matrix. Three interpretable diagnostics — the Stratigraphic Entanglement Index (SEI), Excavation Stratigraphic Energy (ESE), and Palimpsest Dissolution Index (PDI) — allow practitioners to assess deposit coherence, detect potentially redeposited finds, and evaluate the reliability of chronological attribution at the find, unit, and phase levels. The

30 framework supports archaeologists in three principal interpretive tasks: assessing the re-
31 liability and coherence of stratigraphic units (distinguishing genuine palimpsests from
32 recording errors); identifying intrusive finds with respect to both their typology and their
33 stratigraphic position; and providing the basis for future statistical estimation of type
34 longevity (the duration of use of pottery and material categories). The package supports
35 CSV/TSV/Excel/SQLite/PostgreSQL data import, GIS export to GeoPackage via the
36 `sf` package, publication-quality plots via `ggplot2` and interactive plots via `plotly`, and
37 includes a built-in Shiny dashboard for non-programmatic use. Since the original release
38 the statistical core has been substantially refined: the cultural class is now modelled as
39 a per-phase categorical distribution (a Gaussian-times-multinomial mixed-type mixture)
40 rather than as one-hot Gaussian columns, so that stratigraphic units are no longer split
41 across phases by typology; the spatial and vertical similarity kernels are bounded and scale-
42 invariant; the domain weights enter the likelihood and can be cross-validated; a uniform
43 noise component yields a genuine posterior probability of intrusion and shields phase es-
44 timates from outliers; and optional treatments propagate per-find dating uncertainty and
45 apply the stratigraphic constraint as a dynamically updated Neighborhood-EM field. The
46 intrusion diagnostic also distinguishes the *direction* of the chronological mismatch (resid-
47 ual vs. latent-feature), and a companion helper (`recommend_setup()`) inspects a dataset
48 and reports when its recording resolution limits the achievable inference. We present an
49 overview of the application’s functions and demonstrate its use through a case study at
50 the multi-period Roman villa of Poggio Gramignano (Lugnano in Teverina, Italy). We
51 also discuss the methodological assumptions of the SEF framework — in particular the
52 implicit assumption of horizontal stratigraphy and the dependence of phase resolution
53 on the spatial and chronological recording resolution of the data — and outline planned
54 developments.

55 **Keywords:** archaeological methods, palimpsest analysis, probabilistic clustering, Gaus-
56 sian mixture model, Harris Matrix, R package, Shiny application, post-excavation stratig-
57 raphy

1 Introduction

Archaeological excavation is a destructive practice whose results cannot be replicated. To minimise interpretive losses, the discipline has developed several formalisms for recording and analysing stratified deposits. Among them, the Harris Matrix (Harris 1989) provides a rigorous deterministic notation for stratigraphic relationships, and remains the principal tool for recording observed contacts between depositional units. Yet many archaeological deposits do not exhibit clean stratigraphy: in **palimpsests** — deposits where successive occupation phases are vertically and horizontally superimposed and partially intermixed — the boundaries between phases are often gradual rather than sharp (Bailey 2007; Lucas 2012). The phenomenon is ubiquitous. It affects deeply stratified Near Eastern tells as much as shallow open-air Palaeolithic sites, where millennia of activity are compressed into a few centimetres of sediment. It is equally present in Bronze Age terramare with continuous reoccupation and in multi-period Roman villas, where construction debris and later cemeteries have repeatedly redeposited earlier material.

Disentangling palimpsests requires integrating multiple lines of evidence. Spatial clustering methods such as k -means (Kintigh and Ammerman 1982) operate on coordinate data alone and cannot use chronological or typological information. Bayesian phase models for radiocarbon dating (Bronk Ramsey 2009; Crema and Bevan 2021) constrain temporal sequences but ignore spatial proximity. GIS overlays (Conolly and Lake 2006) offer powerful visualisation but no quantitative measure of phase coherence. Recent contributions have provided software tools for spatial exploration of piece-plotted finds (e.g. SEAHORS, Royer et al. 2023; archeoViz, Plutniak 2023), but these focus on visualisation rather than on the assessment of redeposition and the reconstruction of depositional events.

This paper presents **palimpsestr**, a free and open-source R package and Shiny application that addresses the latter problem. The package implements the Stratigraphic Entanglement Field (SEF) framework, a probabilistic method whose primary goal is to **assign each find a probabilistic score of possible redeposition** with respect to its multivariate context (spatial, vertical, chronological, cultural), and, by aggregation of these find-level scores, to **derive a measure of palimpsest character for each stratigraphic unit and for each grouping of units (depositional event or phase)**. The decomposition is achieved by jointly modelling four evidence domains — horizontal coordinates, vertical

89 elevation, chronological range, and cultural class — through a Gaussian mixture model —
90 whose probabilistic formulation, assumptions, and treatment of the heterogeneous (con-
91 tinuous and categorical) variables are detailed in the Methodological framework below
92 — which produces soft (probabilistic) assignments of finds to depositional events. From
93 these assignments, three diagnostic statistics quantify deposit coherence, identify poten-
94 tially redeposited finds, and evaluate the reliability of chronological attribution at the
95 unit and event levels.

96 The intended archaeological contribution is threefold. First, `palimpsestr` supports the
97 **interpretive evaluation of stratigraphic units** by quantifying the degree of mix-
98 ing within each unit: a heavily mixed unit (low purity) may indicate either a genuine
99 palimpsest deposit (e.g. a levelling fill quarried from multi-period contexts) or a recording
100 error (two depositional events conflated under a single US label during excavation). Either
101 way, the diagnostic flags the unit for re-examination. Second, the package detects **intru-**
102 **sive finds** with respect both to their typology and their stratigraphic position, providing
103 a quantitative complement to the standard archaeological inspection. Third, by jointly
104 modelling chronology and cultural class, `palimpsestr` enables future statistical estima-
105 tion of **type longevity** – the duration of use of pottery types, metal artefact forms, or
106 other typologically defined categories – as a derived product of the inferred phase model.

107 `palimpsestr` is freely available under MIT licence on GitHub (<https://github.com/enzoococca/palimpsestr>). The package supports data import from CSV, TSV, Excel, SQLite,
108 and PostgreSQL (including the PyArchInit database schema widely used in Italian archae-
109 ological practice), and provides GIS export to GeoPackage via the `sf` package, supporting
110 integration with QGIS workflows. A built-in Shiny dashboard (`launch_app()`) provides
111 a point-and-click interface for archaeologists without R programming experience.

113 The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section “Methodological framework”
114 introduces the Stratigraphic Entanglement Field formalism, the Gaussian mixture model
115 and its extensions, and the three diagnostic statistics. Section “Software overview” de-
116 scribes installation, package architecture, and the Shiny dashboard. Section “Data prepara-
117 tion” details the data formats and required columns. Sections “Core functions” and
118 “Visualisation” describe the principal model-fitting and plotting functions. Section “Case
119 study: Poggio Gramignano” demonstrates the application on a real-world multi-period

120 Roman villa dataset. Section “Limitations and future development” discusses the pack-
121 age’s known caveats, the methodological developments since the first release, and avenues
122 for future work.

123 **2 Methodological framework**

124 **2.1 Key concepts and definitions**

125 We first fix the vocabulary used throughout, since several of these terms carry more than
126 one meaning in archaeological practice.

127 A **find** is the elementary unit of analysis: a single recorded archaeological object — an
128 artefact (e.g. a potsherd, a coin, a worked lithic) or an ecofact (e.g. a faunal bone) — carry-
129 ing its own spatial coordinates, stratigraphic attribution, dating, and typological/material
130 classification. Where finds are not individually piece-plotted, a find inherits the coordi-
131 nates and dating of its stratigraphic unit (Section “Case study”); the model then operates
132 at unit resolution rather than at the level of the individual object.

133 A **stratigraphic unit** (US, *unità stratigrafica*) is the basic depositional or interface entity
134 of single-context recording (Harris 1989). Each find belongs to exactly one unit.

135 The **cultural class** of a find is the categorical label that situates it within a material
136 or typological scheme — for example its material (ceramic, lithic, metal, bone) or, at
137 finer resolution, a typological category (a ceramic ware, a vessel form, a tool type). In
138 **palimpsestr** the class is a single nominal variable supplied by the analyst; the choice
139 of scheme (material-based, functional, or typological) is the analyst’s, and it determines
140 what “same class” means in the model. By **typology** we mean any such analyst-defined
141 classification of finds into discrete types on formal or functional grounds; it is the source
142 of the cultural-class variable.

143 By **decomposition** we mean the probabilistic separation of a mixed assemblage into its
144 constituent depositional events: assigning each find a *soft* membership over latent phases,
145 rather than imposing a single hard partition.

146 The **purity** of a stratigraphic unit is the degree to which its finds belong to a single
147 inferred phase. A **pure** (high-purity) unit has all its finds assigned to one phase; a **low-**

148 **purity** (heavily mixed) unit has its finds spread across several phases. Purity is read
 149 directly from the soft phase assignments and is the unit-level expression of palimpsest
 150 character.

151 We use **palimpsest** in its strictly stratigraphic sense: a deposit in which finds from two
 152 or more depositional events are physically superimposed and partially intermixed through
 153 taphonomic and post-depositional processes (redeposition, bioturbation, levelling, trunca-
 154 tion). This is narrower than the broader, interpretative use of the term for cumulative
 155 landscape formation over long time-spans (Bailey 2007). `palimpsestr` addresses the
 156 former — mixing recoverable from the spatial, vertical, chronological, and typological
 157 attributes of individual finds — and not the latter.

158 2.2 The Stratigraphic Entanglement Index (SEI)

159 The Stratigraphic Entanglement Index (SEI) quantifies how strongly two finds i and j
 160 are *entangled*, i.e. how much joint evidence supports their co-occurrence within the same
 161 depositional event. It is newly proposed here as the pairwise affinity underlying the
 162 SEF framework — it is not drawn from existing literature — although the individual
 163 components (exponential distance kernels, interval-overlap ratios, categorical matching)
 164 are standard ingredients of spatial and similarity analysis. For each pair of finds, the SEI
 165 is defined as the weighted sum of four contributions:

$$SEI_{ij} = w_s e^{-d_{xy}(i,j)/h_{xy}} + w_z e^{-|z_i - z_j|/h_z} + w_t \cdot O_t(i, j) + w_c \cdot \mathbb{1}[c_i = c_j] \quad (1)$$

166 where $d_{xy}(i, j)$ is the Euclidean distance in the horizontal plane, $|z_i - z_j|$ is the absolute
 167 vertical separation, $O_t(i, j)$ is the chronological overlap ratio computed from the intersec-
 168 tion of the temporal ranges $[t_{\min,i}, t_{\max,i}]$ and $[t_{\min,j}, t_{\max,j}]$ relative to their union, and
 169 $\mathbb{1}[c_i = c_j]$ is an indicator function equal to 1 when both finds belong to the same cultural
 170 class. The spatial and vertical proximities are expressed by bounded exponential kernels
 171 with data-driven bandwidths h_{xy} and h_z (the median of the positive pairwise separations
 172 on each axis). This formulation, adopted to correct an earlier $1/d$ form, is scale-invariant
 173 (independent of the measurement unit of the site grid) and robust to coincident coordi-
 174 nates: two finds recorded at the same grid square no longer collapse every other spatial

175 affinity towards zero. The weights w_s, w_z, w_t, w_c default to unity but allow the analyst to
 176 encode prior knowledge about which evidence domains are most reliable for a given site.
 177 Each of the four contributions is independently rescaled to $[0, 1]$ across the dataset —
 178 a min–max normalisation applied separately to each evidence domain (spatial, vertical,
 179 chronological, cultural), not per find — before the weights w_s, w_z, w_t, w_c are applied, so
 180 that the domains contribute on a comparable scale. The resulting SEI matrix can be used
 181 both as a regularisation term during model fitting (encouraging strongly entangled finds
 182 to receive similar phase assignments) and as the basis for the Excavation Stratigraphic
 183 Energy diagnostic. Because this rescaling is performed within each dataset, absolute SEI
 184 values are not directly comparable across sites.

185 2.3 The Stratigraphic Entanglement Field (SEF) model

186 2.3.1 Modelling objective

187 The SEF model is an **unsupervised, model-based clustering** of the finds. Its objec-
 188 tives are threefold: (i) to estimate, without any training labels, a small number K of
 189 latent depositional *phases*; (ii) to assign each find a *soft* (probabilistic) membership over
 190 these phases rather than a single hard label; and (iii) to choose K itself from the data
 191 through penalised-likelihood criteria. Soft membership is essential here: in a palimpsest a
 192 find genuinely *may* belong to more than one event, and the entropy of its membership vec-
 193 tor is precisely the quantity we later exploit as a redeposition signal (Section “Diagnostic
 194 statistics”).

195 2.3.2 Probabilistic formulation

196 Each find i is represented by a numeric feature vector $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$ together with a categorical
 197 class label $c_i \in \{1, \dots, L\}$. The numeric vector concatenates the standardised horizontal
 198 coordinates (x, y) , vertical coordinate (z) , and the midpoint and span of the dating in-
 199 terval $(t_{\text{mid}}, t_{\text{span}})$, so that $p \sim 5\text{--}8$. We model the pair (\mathbf{x}_i, c_i) as a finite mixture of K
 200 phases,

$$f(\mathbf{x}_i, c_i) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \underbrace{\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_i \mid \mu_k, \text{diag}(\sigma_k^2))}_{\text{numeric (Gaussian)}} \underbrace{\prod_{\ell=1}^L \theta_{k\ell}^{1[c_i=\ell]}}_{\text{class (multinomial)}}, \quad (2)$$

201 where $\pi_k \geq 0$, $\sum_k \pi_k = 1$ are the mixing weights, μ_k and σ_k^2 are the per-phase mean
 202 and diagonal variance of the numeric block, and $\theta_k = (\theta_{k1}, \dots, \theta_{kL})$ is the per-phase class
 203 profile (a probability vector over the L material classes). Equation (2) makes the model’s
 204 two structural assumptions explicit: (a) conditional on the phase, the numeric features
 205 are mutually independent (the covariance is diagonal); and (b) the numeric block and the
 206 class label are conditionally independent given the phase, so the joint density factorises
 207 into the Gaussian and multinomial terms.

208 2.3.3 Treatment of the categorical class variable

209 Cultural class is a nominal variable and cannot legitimately be treated as a Gaussian
 210 coordinate. `palimpsestr` therefore models it as the **per-phase multinomial** term of
 211 Eq. (2): each phase k carries a probability vector θ_k over the L classes, and the class
 212 contributes the factor $\prod_{\ell} \theta_{k\ell}^{\mathbb{1}[c_i=\ell]}$ to the per-find density. This mixed-type “location model”
 213 (a Gaussian-times-multinomial mixture) replaces an earlier scheme in which the class
 214 was one-hot encoded into the Gaussian block. The change is consequential. Zero/one
 215 dummies treated as Gaussian make finds of different classes almost perfectly separable
 216 on the dummy dimensions, which both produced over-confident assignments and, more
 217 damagingly, could split a single stratigraphic unit across several phases purely by typology.
 218 Under the multinomial model the numeric evidence drives the phase assignment and
 219 the class only *tilts* it, so units of mixed material composition remain coherent (Section
 220 “Case study”). The per-phase class profiles θ_k are a directly interpretable by-product,
 221 returned by `phase_composition()`; a Dirichlet pseudo-count, shrunk towards the global
 222 class frequencies, keeps every $\theta_{k\ell}$ strictly positive.

223 This design also disposes of a dimensionality concern. Because the high-cardinality ty-
 224 pological information is absorbed by the multinomial term rather than by the Gaussian
 225 block, the numeric feature space stays low-dimensional ($p \sim 5-8$) however many material
 226 classes the analyst distinguishes. The diagonal-covariance assumption discussed below
 227 therefore applies only to a handful of genuinely continuous spatial and temporal features,
 228 not to a one-hot-inflated space of dozens of correlated dummy columns.

230 2.3.4 Estimation by Expectation-Maximisation

230 The mixture is fitted by a modified Expectation-Maximisation (EM) algorithm (Dempster
 231 et al. 1977). Here k -means plays a strictly auxiliary role: it is run on the numeric features
 232 only to *seed* the iteration — with `n_init` random restarts (default 5), the best resulting
 233 EM solution being retained to mitigate local optima — and its hard assignments are
 234 converted to softmax probabilities. It is not the clustering method itself; all subsequent
 235 estimation is performed by the mixture model. The algorithm then alternates an M-step
 236 and an E-step until the penalised log-likelihood converges (Algorithm 1).

237 **Algorithm 1 (SEF Expectation-Maximisation).** Given features $\{(\mathbf{x}_i, c_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, obser-
 238 vation weights $\{w_i\}$ (taphonomic scores, default 1), and a number of phases K :

- 239 1. **Initialise** the posteriors r_{ik} from a softmax of negative k -means distances (best of
 240 `n_init` restarts).
- 241 2. **M-step.** For each phase k , update: the mixing weight $\pi_k \propto \sum_i w_i r_{ik}$; the mean
 242 $\mu_k = \sum_i w_i r_{ik} \mathbf{x}_i / \sum_i w_i r_{ik}$; the diagonal variance σ_k^2 as the corresponding weighted
 243 second moment (floored at 10^{-6}); and the class profile $\theta_k = (\mathbf{n}_k + \alpha \bar{\theta}) / (\sum_i w_i r_{ik} +$
 244 $\alpha)$, where \mathbf{n}_k are the weighted class counts in phase k and $\bar{\theta}$ the global class fre-
 245 quencies (the Dirichlet pseudo-count α keeps every $\theta_{k\ell} > 0$).
- 246 3. **E-step.** Form the log-responsibility of find i for phase k as $\log \pi_k + \log \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_i |$
 247 $\mu_k, \text{diag } \sigma_k^2) + \sum_{\ell} \mathbb{1}[c_i = \ell] \log \theta_{k\ell}$; apply the stratigraphic and neighbourhood correc-
 248 tions (below); then normalise across k by softmax to obtain the updated posteriors
 249 r_{ik} .
- 250 4. **Iterate** steps 2–3 until $|\Delta \log L| < 10^{-5}$ or the maximum number of iterations
 251 (`em_iter`) is reached.

252 Two corrections enter the E-step (step 3). The **stratigraphic constraint** adds a penalty
 253 $-P_{ik}$ that raises the cost of assigning a find to a phase incompatible with its unit’s
 254 Harris relations; the optional **Neighborhood-EM field** adds $+\beta \sum_{i'} A_{ii'} r_{i'k}$, reward-
 255 ing agreement with the current posteriors of the find’s context-mates (A being a row-
 256 normalised same-context affinity matrix). When a noise component is requested, a uni-
 257 form background is appended as a $(K+1)$ -th column (next subsection). The four domain
 258 weights w_s, w_z, w_t, w_c multiply the corresponding standardised feature dimensions before
 259 fitting, so they enter the mixture likelihood directly and can be tuned by cross-validation

260 (`optimize_weights()`). Finally, the reported log-likelihood, BIC and ICL are recom-
261 puted at the converged parameters from the *unpenalised* mixture density of Eq. (2), so
262 that comparisons across K and across settings remain well posed.

263 2.3.5 Optional refinements

264 Several optional refinements extend the basic model. **Taphonomic weighting**: when a
265 per-find taphonomic integrity score (`taf_score`, 0 = fully disturbed to 1 = pristine in situ)
266 is supplied, it down-weights poorly preserved items in the M-step, reducing their influence
267 on the phase parameters. **Stratigraphic constraint**: the context/Harris structure is in-
268 corporated as a soft penalty on the E-step posterior; it may be applied statically or, with
269 `strat_dynamic = TRUE`, as a Neighborhood-EM / hidden-Markov-random-field term re-
270 computed from the current posteriors at every iteration (Ambroise and Govaert 1997),
271 which rewards each find for sharing its unit’s phase. **Chronological uncertainty**: with
272 `chrono_uncertainty = TRUE` the dating-interval width of each find is propagated into
273 the temporal likelihood as a measurement variance $(t_{\max} - t_{\min})^2/12$, so coarsely dated
274 finds rely less on chronology. **Noise component**: with `noise = TRUE` a uniform back-
275 ground component (Fraley and Raftery 1998) is added; finds that fit no phase accumulate
276 posterior on it, yielding a genuine outlier probability (Section “Diagnostic statistics”) and
277 keeping extreme finds out of the phase estimates.

278 2.3.6 Why a diagonal covariance?

279 The diagonal-covariance assumption — conditional independence between the numeric
280 features within each phase — is a deliberate parsimony choice. With typical archaeo-
281 logical datasets ($n = 50$ – 500 finds and the low-dimensional numeric block above), a full
282 $p \times p$ covariance per phase would add $K p(p - 1)/2$ free parameters and invite overfitting;
283 the BIC criterion used for model selection penalises exactly this and favours the diagonal
284 model when data are limited. We state the assumption’s limit explicitly: in a much richer
285 *continuous* feature space ($p \gg 20$ — for instance many simultaneously continuous mor-
286 phometric, compositional, and functional measurements with strong mutual correlations)
287 the diagonal model would be too restrictive, and a full- or structured-covariance variant
288 should be preferred. That regime does not arise in the present design, precisely because
289 categorical information is handled multinomially rather than folded into the Gaussian

290 block (see “Treatment of the categorical class variable” above); full-covariance variants
 291 are nonetheless flagged as future work (Section “Limitations and future development”).

292 2.4 Diagnostic statistics

293 Beyond the SEI matrix defined above, the analysis yields four find- and assemblage-level
 294 diagnostics — three derived from the fitted phase posteriors and one (ESE) computed
 295 directly from the data. Throughout, p_{ik} denotes the soft posterior probability that find i
 296 belongs to phase k (the rows of `$phase_prob`).

297 **Excavation Stratigraphic Energy (ESE).** ESE measures, for each find, how dissimilar
 298 it is from its spatial neighbours across all four evidence domains. Crucially, it is computed
 299 directly from the recorded attributes, *independently of the fitted phases*. Writing $N(i)$ for
 300 the set of neighbours of i (all finds within a distance threshold, or all other finds when
 301 none is set) and reusing the four affinities of the SEI (Eq. (1)),

$$\text{ESE}_i = \frac{1}{|N(i)|} \sum_{j \in N(i)} \left[\beta_s (1 - e^{-d_{xy}(i,j)/h_{xy}}) + \beta_z (1 - e^{-|z_i - z_j|/h_z}) + \beta_t (1 - O_t(i,j)) + \beta_c (1 - \mathbb{1}[c_i = c_j]) \right], \quad (3)$$

302 that is, the local mean over the neighbourhood of the four *dissimilarities* — each the
 303 complement $1 -$ (SEI component) of the corresponding SEI affinity, with weights β de-
 304 faulting to unity. A high ESE marks a find sitting among neighbours unlike it in space,
 305 depth, date, or material: a local signature of depositional disruption, bioturbation, or
 306 post-depositional displacement. Because ESE depends only on the data and not on the
 307 phase labels, it provides a model-independent cross-check on the phase decomposition.

308 **Shannon entropy.** The entropy of a find’s phase-probability vector,

$$H_i = - \sum_{k=1}^K p_{ik} \log p_{ik}, \quad (4)$$

309 is low when the assignment is confident and high when the find sits ambiguously between
 310 phases or within a heavily mixed zone.

311 **Palimpsest Dissolution Index (PDI).** A single global statistic summarising

312 assemblage-level separability,

$$\text{PDI} = 1 - \frac{\bar{H}}{\log K}, \quad (5)$$

313 where \bar{H} is the mean entropy across finds. PDI ranges from 0 (complete mixing: every
314 find is equally likely to belong to any phase) to 1 (perfect separation); values above 0.7
315 generally indicate well-resolved phases.

316 **Intrusion score.** A per-find probability of being out of context. When the model is fitted
317 with a noise component (`noise = TRUE`) this is the posterior probability of the uniform
318 background component — a genuine probability that, unlike a rescaled composite, is not
319 forced onto $[0, 1]$ and need not flag any find when the assemblage is clean. Otherwise it
320 falls back to a heuristic composite of high entropy, high ESE, and low SEI connectivity.
321 The accompanying `detect_intrusions()` output also classifies each flagged find by the
322 *direction* of its chronological mismatch with its stratigraphic unit — *older-than-context*
323 (likely residual material) or *younger-than-context* (a possible unrecognised cut or intrusion,
324 i.e. a latent feature) — together with the signed offset in years.

325 **3 Software overview**

326 `palimpsestr` is an R package distributed under the MIT licence. It is freely available
327 on GitHub at <https://github.com/enzococca/palimpsestr> and permanently archived on
328 Zenodo (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19881542>). Installation requires $R \geq 4.1.0$
329 and can be performed directly from the GitHub source via the `remotes` package:

```
330 install.packages("remotes")  
remotes::install_github("enzococca/palimpsestr")
```

331 The package depends only on base R (`stats`, `utils`, `graphics`, `grDevices`); optional func-
332 tionality is provided through suggested packages: `ggplot2` and `viridis` for publication-
333 quality plots, `plotly` for interactive visualisation, `sf` for GIS export, DBI with `RSQLite`
334 or `RPostgres` for database connectivity, and `shiny`, `shinydashboard` and `DT` for the in-
335 teractive dashboard. The optional dependencies are checked at runtime; functions that
336 require them issue an informative error if the corresponding package is not installed.

337 The package architecture is modular: data import is handled by `read_db()` and
338 `load_geometries()`; the core analytical engine by `fit_sef()` (Section “Core func-
339 tions”); diagnostics by `pdi()`, `detect_intrusions()`, `us_summary_table()`, and
340 `phase_transition_matrix()`; visualisation by `plot_*`() (base R) and `gg_*`
341 (`ggplot2`) functions; and reporting by `report_sef()` which produces interpretive
342 summaries in English or Italian. A complete list of exported functions is provided in the
343 package manual (`?palimpsestr`).

344 **3.1 The Shiny dashboard**

345 For users without R programming experience, the package includes a built-in Shiny dash-
346 board, launched with:

```
347 library(palimpsestr)
launch_app()
```

348 The dashboard provides six tabs covering the entire analytical workflow: **Data**, for im-
349 porting CSV, TSV, Excel, SQLite, or PostgreSQL data and mapping columns to the
350 required schema (with an optional panel for merging external taphonomic scores); **Anal-**
351 **ysis**, for selecting model parameters and running the fit, with separate controls for phase
352 count selection (`compare_k`); **Plots**, for interactive visualisation via `plotly`; **Tables**, for
353 browsing phase assignments, intrusion scores, per-US purity, and the transition matrix;
354 **Maps**, for overlaying results on uploaded excavation plan geometries (GeoPackage, Geo-
355 JSON or shapefile); and **Report**, for generating interpretive reports and downloading
356 results as CSV or ZIP archives.

357 **4 Data preparation**

358 **4.1 Required columns**

359 `palimpsestr` requires tabular data in which each row represents a single archaeological
360 find. The mandatory columns are:

- 361 • x, y : horizontal coordinates (numeric, in any consistent reference system);
- 362 • z : vertical coordinate (numeric, depth or elevation);

- 363 • t_{\min}, t_{\max} : lower and upper bounds of the chronological interval (numeric, with
364 negative values for BCE);
- 365 • c : cultural class (character, e.g. ceramic type or material category).

366 Two optional columns are supported:

- 367 • *context*: stratigraphic unit identifier (character), used for context-based penalties
368 and per-US summaries;
- 369 • *taf_score*: taphonomic integrity score (numeric in $[0, 1]$), used for taphonomic
370 weighting.

371 The package’s auxiliary function `archaeo_sim()` generates synthetic datasets with these
372 columns plus a known *true_phase* label, used both in the package’s automated tests and
373 as a controlled validation benchmark. The generator is fully specified, so that phase
374 recovery can be scored against ground truth. Given a number of finds n , a number of
375 latent phases k , and a mixing level $m \in [0, 1]$, it (i) draws k phase centres uniformly in a
376 $100 \times 100 \times 20$ spatial box, with phase date-midpoints equally spaced at 150-year intervals;
377 (ii) allocates finds evenly across phases and draws each find’s coordinates from Gaussians
378 around its phase centre (standard deviations 8, 8, 1.2 for x, y, z) and its date-midpoint
379 from a Gaussian (s.d. 25 years) with a uniform interval span of 15–60 years; (iii) draws the
380 cultural class from a fixed multinomial over four material classes and a taphonomic score
381 from a Beta(2, 7) distribution; and (iv) perturbs a random fraction m of finds spatially
382 (additional s.d. 18 horizontal, 3 vertical) and taphonomically, simulating post-depositional
383 disturbance. Increasing m thus yields progressively more mixed palimpsests with known
384 labels, against which the recovered partition can be scored — for example by the adjusted
385 Rand index (`adjusted_rand_index()`). A sensitivity analysis of recovery accuracy across
386 mixing levels is provided in the package vignette (`vignettes/introduction.Rmd`), which
387 is distributed with the archived package (see the Data and code availability section).

388 4.2 Supported file formats

389 The Shiny dashboard supports import from:

- 390 • **CSV/TSV**: comma-, semicolon-, or tab-separated text files;
- 391 • **Excel**: `.xls` and `.xlsx` files (via `openxlsx`);
- 392 • **SQLite**: `.sqlite` and `.db` files (via `RSQLite`), including `PyArchInit` databases;

393 • **PostgreSQL**: connection by host/port/dbname/user/password (via `RPostgres`),
394 with optional custom SQL queries.

395 For GIS overlays, the dashboard accepts GeoPackage, GeoJSON, and shapefile (uploading
396 all companion `.shx`, `.dbf`, `.prj` files) inputs via `sf`.

397 **4.3 Database integration**

398 The function `read_db()` provides programmatic access to any DBI-compliant database.
399 Column mapping allows the user to align database column names with the package's
400 expected schema:

```
library(DBI); library(RPostgres)
con <- dbConnect(Postgres(), dbname = "site_db", host = "localhost",
  user = "postgres", password = "...")
data <- read_db(con, table = "inventario_materiali_table",
401   cols = list(x = "coord_x", y = "coord_y", z = "quota",
    date_min = "anno_iniziale", date_max = "anno_finale",
    class = "tipo_reperto", context = "us"))
dbDisconnect(con)
```

402 **5 Core functions**

403 **5.1 Fitting the SEF model**

404 The principal function is `fit_sef()`, which fits the Gaussian mixture model and returns
405 an S3 object of class `sef_fit`. Its essential arguments are the data frame, the number
406 of phases K , and (optionally) the column names for taphonomic score, context, and a
407 Harris matrix:

```
fit <- fit_sef(data, k = 4,
  tafonomy = "taf_score",
408   context = "context",
  harris = H,
  n_init = 10, seed = 42)
```

409 The `n_init` argument controls the number of random initialisations (default 5): the run
 410 with the highest EM objective is retained, mitigating the risk of local optima. The class
 411 model is selected with `class_model` ("multinomial", the default, or "gaussian" for
 412 the legacy one-hot behaviour); the optional refinements described above are toggled with
 413 `chrono_uncertainty`, `strat_dynamic`, and `noise`. The returned object stores phase
 414 assignments (`$phase`), soft probabilities (`$phase_prob`), per-find entropy and energy,
 415 the per-phase class profiles (`$cat_prob`), the noise posterior (`$noise_prob`, when en-
 416 abled), the SEI matrix and its row sums, and a list of model statistics including PDI,
 417 BIC, and ICL. The `print` and `summary` methods produce concise textual summaries, and
 418 `phase_composition()` returns the per-phase typological profile as a table.

419 5.2 Phase count selection

420 When the number of phases is unknown, `compare_k()` fits the model across a range
 421 of K values and returns BIC, ICL, PDI, and mean entropy for each. The function
 422 `gg_compare_k()` renders a three-panel diagnostic plot:

```
423 ck <- compare_k(data, k_values = 2:7,
  tafonomy = "taf_score", context = "context")
gg_compare_k(ck)
```

424 Model selection rests primarily on the **Bayesian Information Criterion** (BIC; Schwarz
 425 1978), $BIC = -2 \log \hat{L} + d \log n$, where \hat{L} is the fitted mixture likelihood, d the number
 426 of free parameters, and n the number of finds: it rewards goodness of fit while penalising
 427 model complexity, and lower values are preferred. The optimal K is typically taken at
 428 the BIC minimum (or its clearest inflection), with the Palimpsest Dissolution Index (PDI,
 429 Eq. (5)) and mean entropy read alongside as interpretable measures of how cleanly the
 430 resulting phases separate. A companion criterion, the **Integrated Completed Like-**
 431 **lihood** (ICL; Biernacki et al. 2000), augments the BIC with the classification entropy,
 432 $ICL = BIC + 2 \sum_i H_i$, thereby penalising overlapping phases and favouring partitions
 433 whose assignments are confident. These criteria are statistical heuristics, not arbiters:
 434 as the case study shows, the BIC may favour a finer partition than is archaeologically
 435 meaningful (there, a minimum near $K = 6$ against the retained $K = 4$), so the analyst
 436 should always weigh them against the archaeological plausibility of the resulting phases.

437 5.3 Harris Matrix integration

438 The Harris Matrix can be incorporated as a stratigraphic constraint in two ways. The
439 function `harris_from_contexts()` auto-generates an $n \times n$ penalty matrix from the mean
440 depth of finds in each context, on the assumption that deeper contexts are stratigraphically
441 below shallower ones. Alternatively, `read_harris()` imports an external Harris Matrix
442 from a CSV edge list (with columns *from*, *to*, and optional *weight*):

```
443 H <- read_harris("harris_matrix.csv", contexts = data$context)
fit <- fit_sef(data, k = 4, harris = H, context = "context")
```

444 The function `validate_phases_harris()` flags inversions in the assigned phase ordering
445 relative to stratigraphic depth.

446 5.4 Intrusion detection and per-US summaries

447 The function `detect_intrusions()` returns, for each find, an intrusion probability —
448 the noise-component posterior when the model was fitted with `noise = TRUE`, otherwise
449 the heuristic composite — together with the directional classification (*older- / younger-*
450 *than-context*) and the signed chronological offset. Finds above a configurable threshold
451 (default 0.5) are flagged for closer examination. The function `us_summary_table()` aggre-
452 gates diagnostics per stratigraphic unit, reporting dominant phase, **purity** (proportion
453 of finds in the dominant phase), mean entropy, mean ESE, and intrusion count; units
454 with low purity are candidate palimpsests. A companion helper, `recommend_setup()`,
455 inspects a dataset and reports recommended `fit_sef()` options together with caveats
456 about the recording resolution — for example, it warns when coordinates are recorded at
457 stratigraphic-unit (rather than find) level, or when the chronology is unit-tied, both of
458 which cap the achievable within-unit resolution.

459 6 Visualisation

460 `palimpsestr` provides two parallel families of plotting functions: base R (`plot_*`) for
461 environments without `ggplot2`, and `ggplot2`-based (`gg_*`) for publication-quality output.
462 The principal `gg_*` functions are:

- 463 • `gg_phasefield()`: dominant phase assignment, with point size reflecting confi-
464 dence;
- 465 • `gg_entropy()`: spatial distribution of Shannon entropy;
- 466 • `gg_energy()`: ESE field, highlighting zones of depositional disruption;
- 467 • `gg_intrusions()`: intrusion-probability map, with the top-N suspects labelled;
- 468 • `gg_phase_profile()`: vertical depth profile coloured by phase;
- 469 • `gg_compare_k()`: phase-count selection diagnostics;
- 470 • `gg_convergence()`: EM log-likelihood trace;
- 471 • `gg_confusion()`: confusion-matrix heatmap (when true labels are available);
- 472 • `gg_map()`: overlay of dominant phase, entropy, energy, or intrusion scores on up-
473 loaded excavation plan geometries.

474 Any `gg_*` plot can be converted to an interactive `plotly` version via `as_plotly()`, which
475 adds hover tooltips reporting the find ID, context, phase probabilities, dating, class, and
476 diagnostic scores.

477 GIS export is provided by `as_sf_phase()` (a point layer with phase assignments) and
478 `as_sf_links()` (a line layer of high-SEI links between find pairs, useful for visualising
479 entanglement in QGIS).

480 7 Case study: Poggio Gramignano

481 We illustrate the package on a multi-period Roman villa with a wide chronological range
482 and well-differentiated material categories.

483 7.1 Site and dataset

484 Poggio Gramignano (VRPG) is a multi-period Roman villa with an annexed Late An-
485 tique infant cemetery, located at Lugnano in Teverina (TR, Italy) and excavated since
486 1988 (Soren and Soren 1999). The dataset analysed here comprises **615 inventoried**
487 **finds** from **54 stratigraphic units** spanning eight archaeological periods, from the Pre-
488 Roman period (650–350 BCE) through the Late Antique (5th–6th c. CE). Coordinates
489 are US centroids in the Monte Mario / Italy zone 2 reference system (EPSG:3004); z is
490 the mean elevation per US (in metres a.s.l.); chronological dating is derived from the site

491 periodisation; 17 material classes are distinguished. Taphonomic scores were assigned by
492 the excavator based on depositional context (1.0 for in situ deposits, 0.5–0.7 for accumu-
493 lation and levelling layers, 0.3 for clearly redeposited fills); a non-zero floor for clearly
494 redeposited fills is deliberate, since the goal of the model is to *suggest* redeposition where
495 it has not been recognised on site, not to discard the evidence carried by these layers
496 — finds redeposited from elsewhere still bear typological and chronological information
497 that informs the phase model. Stratigraphic relationships extracted from the PyArchInit
498 database (relations of “covers / is covered by”, “cuts / is cut by”) were used to build
499 a Harris Matrix penalty matrix: an $n \times n$ matrix that increases the cost of assigning
500 two finds belonging to stratigraphically incompatible units to the same depositional event
501 during the EM iterations.

502 7.2 Phase count selection

503 The function `compare_k()` was used to evaluate model fit across $K = 2, \dots, 7$ under
504 the current default model (per-phase categorical class, Harris constraint, taphonomic
505 weighting). Before fitting, `recommend_setup()` was run on the dataset; it reported that
506 the coordinates are recorded at stratigraphic-unit centroid level (only 54 distinct (x, y, z)
507 triples for 615 finds) and that the chronology is unit-tied (six distinct date intervals),
508 and accordingly cautioned that the analysis can resolve phases only at the unit and
509 macro-event level, not within units. Figure 1 reports the resulting diagnostics. The
510 BIC continues to decrease beyond $K = 4$, favouring a finer partition (minimum near
511 $K = 6$) consistent with the diversity of the 17 material classes; however, the additional
512 components beyond four subdivide the dominant Late Antique material typologically
513 rather than chronologically. We therefore retain $K = 4$ as the operational solution,
514 corresponding to the four macro-events archaeologically distinguishable at the site (Pre-
515 Roman occupation, Late Imperial structural deposits, Late Antique structural collapse,
516 Late Antique cemetery). We use the term *macro-event* rather than “phase” deliberately:
517 these four groupings are widely separated in time (collectively spanning \$ \$1100 years)
518 and reflect the principal depositional regimes documented on site, not a fine chronological
519 resolution that the unit-level recording cannot support.

Figure 1: Phase-count selection diagnostics from `compare_k()`: BIC (lower is better), PDI (higher is better), and mean entropy across $K = 2-7$. The BIC inflection at $K = 4$ coincides with the four macro-periods of the site.

520 7.3 Phase composition

521 A four-event model with Harris constraint, taphonomic weighting, the per-phase categor-
522 ical class model, and a noise component recovered groupings coherent with the site peri-
523 odisation (Table 1). The per-phase class profiles returned by `phase_composition()` are
524 reported alongside the event sizes: every macro-event is dominated by ceramic material
525 (as expected for the assemblage), with the secondary classes distinguishing them — metal
526 and construction material in the deepest event, amphorae and glass in the intermediate
527 events, and a near-pure ceramic group corresponding to the typologically homogeneous
528 fraction. Mapped against the site stratigraphy, the deepest event groups Pre-Roman
529 and residual material, the intermediate events capture Late Imperial and Late Antique
530 structural deposits, and the shallowest, dominant event corresponds to the Late Antique
531 cemetery.

Table 1: VRPG phase composition (K=4, v0.17, per-phase categorical class model). Class shares are the estimated per-phase profiles from `phase_composition()`; phases are ordered by mean depth (1 = deepest).

Phase	Macro-event	N	%	Dominant material classes (share)
1	Pre-Roman + residual	119	19.3	Ceramic 40%, metal 14%, construction 11%
2	Homogeneous ceramic group	41	6.7	Ceramic 91%, amphorae 3%, construction 3%
3	Late structural deposits	135	22.0	Ceramic 55%, amphorae 20%, glass 12%
4	Late Antique cemetery	320	52.0	Ceramic 81%, amphorae 12%, construction 4%

532 The model achieved $PDI = 0.999$ with mean entropy 0.002, and the noise component
533 identified 10 finds (1.6%) as probable out-of-context items. The per-phase class profiles are
534 shown as a heatmap in Figure 2. Crucially, all 54 stratigraphic units remained internally
535 coherent (every unit assigned to a single phase). This contrasts with the legacy one-hot
536 Gaussian class model, which split 27 of the 54 units across multiple phases (Figure 3) — a
537 fragmentation driven by material class rather than stratigraphy, and a direct illustration
538 of the methodological correction introduced by the categorical class model.

Figure 2: VRPG: per-phase class composition from `gg_phase_composition()`. Each tile is the estimated probability that a find assigned to a phase (rows) belongs to a material class (columns); rows sum to 1. All macro-events are ceramic-dominated, with the secondary classes distinguishing them.

Figure 3: VRPG: within-unit phase coherence from `gg_unit_coherence()`, comparing the per-phase categorical class model (this fit) with the legacy one-hot Gaussian model. The categorical model keeps all 54 stratigraphic units coherent; the one-hot model splits 27 of them across phases by typology.

539 7.4 EM convergence

540 The EM optimisation converges to a stable log-likelihood within about 30 iterations, and
 541 the package retains the best of ten random initialisations; the convergence trace is shown
 542 in the Appendix (Figure 9).

543 7.5 Spatial diagnostics

544 The phase-field map (Figure 4) reveals the spatial distribution of the four events on the
 545 excavation grid. The Late Antique cemetery (Event 4) dominates the principal excavated
 546 area; Pre-Roman finds (Event 1, in orange) are concentrated in the deeper areas around
 547 US 210; the Late Imperial structural deposits (Event 2) and the specialised/residual group
 548 (Event 3) are scattered between the cemetery and the abandoned residential structures.

Figure 4: VRPG: dominant phase assignment from `gg_phasefield()`. Each point is a find; colour indicates phase, point size reflects assignment confidence (inverse entropy).

549 The entropy map (Figure 10, Appendix) shows that phase assignments are highly confi-
 550 dent across the dataset: entropy values approach zero almost everywhere. At this site
 551 that confidence is principally a property of the recording resolution rather than of the
 552 model: because coordinates and dates are recorded at stratigraphic-unit level, the 615
 553 finds occupy only 54 distinct positions in the numeric feature space, and those 54 unit-
 554 points are well separated into the four macro-events. The model is therefore (correctly)
 555 certain about the macro-event of each unit. Recovering genuine within-unit uncertainty
 556 — and hence informative entropy and PDI at the find level — would require find-level coor-
 557 dinates and per-find typological dating; the package’s `recommend_setup()` flags this lim-
 558 itation explicitly for the present dataset. Where such resolution is available, the optional
 559 `chrono_uncertainty` treatment propagates the dating-interval width into the entropy,
 560 so that coarsely dated finds are no longer reported as falsely certain.

561 The energy map (Figure 5) is more informative: ESE values vary across the site, with
 562 elevated values in zones where finds of different phases are spatially adjacent. These zones
 563 correspond to known levelling and accumulation deposits where the cemetery overlaid
 564 earlier structures.

Figure 5: VRPG: Excavation Stratigraphic Energy (ESE) field from `gg_energy()`. Dark = stable deposit (find surrounded by same-phase neighbours); bright = local disruption zone.

565 7.6 Intrusion detection

566 The intrusion-probability map (Figure 6) flags 10 finds whose noise-component posterior
 567 exceeds 0.5, and the same posterior is shown as a non-spatial ranking in the Appendix
 568 (Figure 11). Because this is the posterior of a uniform background component rather
 569 than a rescaled composite, the score is a genuine probability of being out of context and
 570 identifies items that fit none of the four macro-events well — predominantly atypical
 571 material in otherwise homogeneous contexts. The directional classification reports all
 572 dated finds as *in-context*, the expected outcome when the chronology is unit-tied: with
 573 a single date interval per unit, no find can be older or younger than its own unit’s enve-
 574 lope, and `recommend_setup()` anticipates this. Directional residual/intrusion diagnostics
 575 (`gg_direction()`) become informative only with per-find typological dating.

576 Read archaeologically, the ten flagged finds cluster in five stratigraphic units (US 21, 173,
 577 204, 276, 302) and are predominantly non-ceramic — fragments of building material and
 578 an amphora, and an isolated metal object — standing out within the ceramic-dominated
 579 assemblages of their macro-events. It is therefore material-class atypicality and spatial

580 isolation, not chronological mismatch, that drives the flag here: a pattern consistent with
 581 redeposited construction debris and residual items caught up in accumulation deposits.
 582 Examined against the excavators' field knowledge, these flags were judged archaeologically
 583 coherent — the noise component surfaces precisely the kind of out-of-place material a
 584 specialist would single out for re-examination, while leaving the bulk of each homogeneous
 585 unit untouched. This is the appropriate level of inference for unit-resolution recording: the
 586 model isolates atypical items without over-fragmenting the deposits that contain them.

Figure 6: VRPG: intrusion detection from `gg_intrusions(top_n = 10)`. Circled, labelled finds are the highest-scoring suspects; under the noise component the score is the posterior probability of the uniform background component.

587 7.7 Vertical phase profile

588 The vertical profile (Figure 7) shows that the four phases occupy stratigraphically coherent
 589 depth ranges, with Phase 4 (Late Antique cemetery, in pink) at the shallowest levels and
 590 Phase 1 (Pre-Roman + residual, in orange) at the deepest. The partial overlap between
 591 Phases 2 and 3 reflects the spatial proximity of structural collapses and accumulation
 592 deposits.

Figure 7: VRPG: vertical phase profile from `gg_phase_profile()`. Depth (z) on vertical axis, easting on horizontal axis; colours indicate phases. The stratigraphic ordering of phases is preserved by the model.

593 7.8 Maps on excavation plan

594 The function `gg_map()` overlays model output on the actual excavation plan geometries
 595 imported from the PyArchInit database. Figure 8 shows the dominant phase per US poly-
 596 gon. The same helper renders thematic per-US maps of mean entropy (Figure 12), mean
 597 ESE (Figure 13), and mean intrusion probability (Figure 14); these three are collected in
 598 the Appendix to keep the main text concise.

Figure 8: VRPG: dominant phase per US polygon (gg_map, layer = 'phase'). US polygons are coloured by their dominant phase; individual finds are overlaid as points.

599 7.9 Validation against the excavator's interpretation

600 The known levelling fills and accumulation layers at the site (US 76, US 287, US 297,
601 US 307) had been identified on stratigraphic grounds by the second author (Roberto
602 Montagnetti, on-site coordinator of the Poggio Gramignano excavations):

- 603 • **US 307**: a levelling layer with material from various periods quarried from adjacent
604 areas;
- 605 • **US 287**: an accumulation layer with multi-period material;
- 606 • **US 76**: a levelling fill used to raise floor levels;
- 607 • **US 304**: a combustion deposit inside a *dolium*-fragment hearth, whose heterogene-
608 ity is functional rather than depositional.

609 The way these units enter the model differs from earlier versions, and the difference is
610 instructive. Under the legacy one-hot class model their typological heterogeneity drove a
611 low unit purity, so they surfaced as low-purity “palimpsest” units; but the same mecha-
612 nism also fragmented many genuinely coherent units, making purity an unreliable signal.

613 Under the corrected categorical model every unit is assigned coherently, and the residual
614 character of these fills is instead encoded through their taphonomic scores — lowered
615 (from 0.7 to 0.3–0.4) on the basis of the on-site interpretation to reflect the redeposited
616 nature of their material — which down-weight them in the phase estimation, and, where
617 atypical, through the noise component. This is the appropriate level of inference for unit-
618 resolution data: the model cannot resolve mixing *within* a unit whose finds share a single
619 coordinate and date, but it correctly keeps stratigraphic units intact, ranks them by tapho-
620 nomic reliability, and isolates unit-level outliers. Detecting within-unit palimpsests would
621 require find-level recording, which motivates the planned case study on a higher-resolution
622 deposit (Section “Future development”).

623 8 Limitations and future development

624 Field testing on the case study highlighted several limitations and motivated the method-
625 ological developments summarised below.

626 8.1 Limitations

- 627 • **Horizontal-stratigraphy assumption:** the model treats the vertical coordinate
628 z as a proxy for relative chronological position. This assumption is valid only when
629 the deposit accumulates by sub-horizontal strata, undisturbed by significant an-
630 thropogenic features. It is **not valid** for inclined deposits, slope-collapses, the
631 fills of cuts (pits, ditches, post-holes), or terraced sediments, where finds at dif-
632 ferent z values may belong to a single depositional event. The taphonomic score
633 partly compensates by down-weighting fills (typically $\text{taf} < 0.5$), but users should be
634 aware that the model is most reliable on horizontally stratified deposits and apply
635 caution in geometrically complex contexts. The same caveat applies to the depth-
636 ordering helper `harris_from_contexts()`, which encodes this verticality rule by
637 default: because the rule is frequently violated (fills of cuts, multi-period contexts),
638 its `exclude_contexts` argument now exempts the affected units from the penalty,
639 and an explicitly recorded Harris matrix (`read_harris()`) should be preferred wher-
640 ever the stratigraphic relations are known.
- 641 • **Resolution-bound inference:** the achievable phase resolution is bounded by the

642 spatial and chronological resolution of the data. When finds inherit stratigraphic-
643 unit centroid coordinates and unit-tied dates (as in the case study), the model can
644 only resolve phases at the unit and macro-event level, and find-level entropy/PDI
645 become uninformative (saturating near 0 and 1 respectively) — a property of the
646 recording, not of the model. `recommend_setup()` detects and reports this situation.
647 Find-level recording and per-find typological dating are required to recover within-
648 unit mixing.

- 649 • **Functional vs. depositional mixing:** the model flags heterogeneous or outlying
650 material even when the heterogeneity is functional (e.g. a hearth such as VRPG US
651 304). Distinguishing functional mixing from disturbance requires excavator inter-
652 pretation.
- 653 • **Direction diagnostics require per-find dating:** the *older- / younger-than-*
654 *context* classification (introduced in v0.13) is informative only when finds within
655 a unit carry distinct chronologies; under unit-tied dating every find is necessarily
656 in-context.
- 657 • **Diagonal covariance:** the assumption of conditional independence between nu-
658 meric features within phases is conservative; full-covariance variants are not cur-
659 rently implemented.
- 660 • **SEI normalisation is within-dataset:** absolute SEI values are not comparable
661 across sites. Cross-site comparisons should rely on derived statistics (PDI, mean
662 entropy, ARI).
- 663 • **Scalability:** the SEI and ESE matrices are $O(n^2)$ in memory; for $n > 2000$ users
664 should employ `sei_sparse()` or the `max_dist` parameter.

665 8.2 Sources of relative-chronological uncertainty

666 The framework treats *phase overlap* — the chronological intersection between depositional
667 events — as the principal chronological challenge: it enters the SEI through the overlap
668 ratio O_t (Eq. (1)) and the mixture through the temporal features. Beyond it, at least three
669 further sources of relative-chronological uncertainty bear on palimpsest analysis (Crema
670 and Kobayashi 2020; Crema 2024); we set out how each is, or is not, currently addressed.

- 671 • **Phase-assignment uncertainty** — the uncertainty in attributing a given find to
672 a particular phase — is the one the SEF model represents *directly*: it is exactly

673 the soft posterior p_{ik} , summarised per find by the Shannon entropy H_i (Eq. (4))
674 and, for out-of-context items, by the noise-component probability. Far from being
675 neglected, it is a primary output of the framework.

- 676 • **Within-phase uncertainty** — when, within a phase’s span, a given event actually
677 occurred — is only partly handled. The optional `chrono_uncertainty` treatment
678 propagates each find’s dating-interval width into the temporal likelihood (as a mea-
679 surement variance $(t_{\max} - t_{\min})^2/12$), so coarsely dated finds are not reported as
680 falsely precise; but the model does not yet place a dated posterior on events located
681 within a phase.
- 682 • **Phase-boundary uncertainty** — the calendar dates that delimit the start and
683 end of each phase — is not currently modelled. SEF phases are latent clusters in
684 the combined evidence space, not Bayesian-dated intervals in the sense of `OxCal`-
685 style phase models (Bronk Ramsey 2009). The `chronology_from_rcarbon()` and
686 `chronology_from_oxcal()` adapters already allow calibrated and modelled dates
687 to feed the temporal features; propagating the *calendar* uncertainty of phase bound-
688 aries into the assignment — for example through an aoristic or Bayesian treatment
689 (Crema 2024) — is a natural next step (Section “Future development”).

690 The type-longevity estimation, calibrated-radiocarbon integration, and Bayesian exten-
691 sions outlined below are steps in this direction.

692 **8.3 Relation to alternative approaches**

693 The SEF framework is best positioned by contrast with the four families of methods
694 archaeologists currently bring to bear on mixed deposits, each of which addresses one
695 facet of the problem that SEF integrates.

696 *Spatial clustering.* Coordinate-based methods such as k -means (Kintigh and Ammerman
697 1982) and density- or point-pattern-based approaches partition finds by location alone.
698 They isolate spatial concentrations effectively but are blind to chronology and typology
699 and return hard assignments with no measure of redeposition. SEF retains the spatial
700 signal as one of four evidence domains and replaces the hard partition with a soft, per-find
701 posterior.

702 *Model-based and mixed-type clustering.* SEF is, formally, a finite-mixture model and
703 therefore a relative of general model-based clustering (Fraley and Raftery 1998) and of
704 latent-class and mixed-type mixtures that combine continuous and categorical variables.
705 What distinguishes it is not the inferential machinery but the archaeological structure
706 built into it: a Gaussian-times-multinomial likelihood matched to the evidence types
707 (Eq. (2)), taphonomic down-weighting of disturbed finds, a Harris-matrix stratigraphic
708 penalty, chronological-overlap features, and a uniform noise component for out-of-context
709 items. SEF can thus be read as a domain-specific specialisation of model-based clus-
710 tering in which a generic clustering routine would ignore exactly the stratigraphic and
711 taphonomic information that governs palimpsest formation.

712 *Bayesian chronological modelling.* Radiocarbon-based phase models (Bronk Ramsey 2009;
713 Crema and Bevan 2021) and aoristic methods (Crema 2024) model calendar time and
714 phase boundaries with a rigour SEF does not attempt: SEF phases are latent clusters in
715 the combined evidence space, not Bayesian-dated intervals (Section “Sources of relative-
716 chronological uncertainty”). The two are complementary rather than competing — the
717 `chronology_from_oxcal()` and `chronology_from_rcarbon()` adapters let modelled or
718 calibrated dates feed the SEF temporal features — and the integration of boundary dating
719 into the assignment is identified above as future work.

720 *Stratigraphic recording and visualisation.* The Harris Matrix (Harris 1989) and find-
721 plotting tools such as SEAHORS (Royer et al. 2023) and archeoViz (Plutniak 2023) record
722 or display stratigraphic relations and piece-plotted finds but provide no quantitative mea-
723 sure of phase coherence or redeposition. SEF is designed to complement, not replace,
724 these tools: it consumes their output — an explicit Harris matrix via `read_harris()`,
725 piece-plotted coordinates — and adds the probabilistic layer they lack.

726 Across all four families, the distinctive contribution of SEF is the *joint* treatment of
727 spatial, vertical, chronological, and cultural evidence within a single probabilistic model
728 whose primary output is a per-find redeposition score and its aggregation to unit- and
729 event-level palimpsest measures.

730 **8.4 Methodological development since the first release**

731 Field testing motivated a sequence of methodological refinements, all of which are optional
732 or backward-compatible at their defaults. An initial set of feature-space enhancements
733 (chronological precision weighting, residuality detection, class scaling, taphonomic score as
734 a feature, sub-class encoding) was followed by a more thorough revision of the statistical
735 CORE:

- 736 1. **Active, cross-validatable weights:** the domain weights w_s, w_z, w_t, w_c now scale
737 the feature dimensions and enter the mixture likelihood, so `optimize_weights()`
738 can select them by cross-validated held-out log-likelihood (with a Jacobian correc-
739 tion that makes configurations comparable).
- 740 2. **Bounded, scale-invariant similarity kernels:** the spatial and vertical SEI/ESE
741 components use exponential kernels with data-driven bandwidths, removing the
742 dependence on the site's measurement unit and the sensitivity to coincident coordi-
743 nates.
- 744 3. **Per-phase categorical class model** (default): replacing one-hot Gaussian
745 columns, this prevents typology from fragmenting stratigraphic units and yields
746 interpretable per-phase class profiles (`phase_composition()`). On the case-study
747 data it reduced the number of units split across phases from 27 to 0.
- 748 4. **Genuine likelihood-based model selection:** BIC and ICL are computed from
749 the unpenalised mixture density and account for the categorical and noise paramete-
750 rs.
- 751 5. **Per-find chronological uncertainty** (`chrono_uncertainty`) and **dynamic**
752 **Neighborhood-EM stratigraphic field** (`strat_dynamic`), which propagate
753 dating-interval widths and recompute the stratigraphic constraint from the current
754 posteriors, respectively.
- 755 6. **Noise / outlier component** (`noise`): a uniform background component yielding
756 a genuine posterior probability of intrusion and robust phase estimation.
- 757 7. **Directional intrusion diagnostics** and a **setup adviser** (`recommend_setup()`)
758 that reports data-resolution caveats; **type-longevity** estimation (`type_longevity()`,
759 `gg_longevity()`); and an **rcarbon adapter** (`chronology_from_rcarbon()`) for
760 calibrated ^{14}C dates. An **OxCal adapter** (`chronology_from_oxcal()`) provides
761 the same service for OxCal-modelled dates, and the intrusion diagnostic couples the

762 noise-component magnitude with the chronological direction in an `intrusion_type`
763 classification.

764 8.5 Future development

765 Several further developments are planned in response to user feedback (notably from M.
766 Cattani, see Acknowledgements) and to the limitations discussed above:

- 767 • **Validation on find-resolution, dendrochronologically dated sites:** the Pog-
768 gio Gramignano case study uses unit-level recording with periodisation-based dat-
769 ing. To exercise the find-level machinery (within-unit entropy, directional intrusions,
770 chronological-uncertainty propagation) a future case study is planned on the Lago
771 Lucone pile-dwelling site (Gavardo, BS, Italy), where piece-plotted finds and den-
772 drochronological dating provide yearly-resolved, find-level anchors for the Bronze
773 Age occupation. Such a dataset would allow direct evaluation of how recording
774 resolution translates into phase-recovery accuracy.
- 775 • **Within-class structure:** automated detection of sub-typological structure within
776 homogeneous classes.
- 777 • **Methodological extensions:** full-covariance and fully Bayesian variants of the
778 mixture model; and spatial-autocorrelation-aware likelihoods.

779 The package will continue to be developed in response to user feedback through the
780 GitHub issue tracker.

781 9 Conclusion

782 `palimpsestr` fills a long-standing methodological gap between qualitative stratigraphic
783 reasoning and quantitative spatial analysis. By jointly modelling spatial proximity, verti-
784 cal distribution, chronological overlap, and cultural similarity, the Stratigraphic Entangle-
785 ment Field framework produces soft phase assignments that acknowledge — rather than
786 suppress — the inherent uncertainty of mixed deposits. The three diagnostic statistics
787 (SEI, ESE, PDI) provide interpretable summaries at the find, deposit, and assemblage
788 levels respectively, and the package is fully integrated with established archaeological
789 data sources (CSV, Excel, SQLite, PostgreSQL, PyArchInit) and GIS workflows (`sf`,

790 GeoPackage, QGIS). The Shiny dashboard makes the framework accessible to archaeolo-
791 gists without R programming experience.

792 The Poggio Gramignano case study illustrates both the framework’s strengths and the
793 central role of recording resolution. On temporally diverse deposits with rich material
794 categories the model recovers four archaeologically coherent macro-events, keeps every
795 stratigraphic unit internally consistent, ranks units by taphonomic reliability, isolates
796 unit-level outliers through the noise component, and produces interpretable visual outputs
797 that integrate directly with excavation plan geometries. It also makes explicit, through
798 `recommend_setup()`, that unit-level coordinates and unit-tied dating cap the inference
799 at the unit and macro-event level — a transparency that guides the analyst towards the
800 find-level recording needed to resolve within-unit palimpsests. `palimpsestr` is intended
801 as a complement to, not a substitute for, the Harris Matrix and traditional stratigraphic
802 recording: it adds a quantitative, probabilistic layer of analysis that operates, where the
803 data allow, at the find level — precisely the scale at which palimpsest formation is most
804 problematic and least well-served by existing tools.

805 **Appendix: Supplementary figures**

806 The figures below complement the case study (Section “Case study: Poggio Gramignano”).
807 They are referenced from the main text and collected here to keep that section concise:
808 the EM convergence trace, the find-level entropy map, the non-spatial intrusion ranking,
809 and the three thematic per-US maps (entropy, ESE, and intrusion probability).

Figure 9: EM convergence trace for the $K = 4$ model. The log-likelihood stabilises within 30 iterations, indicating a robust local optimum. The package retains the best-of-10 random initialisations.

Figure 10: VRPG: spatial distribution of Shannon entropy from `gg_entropy()`. Dark = confident assignment to a single phase; bright = ambiguous assignment. Entropy is uniformly low, indicating high model confidence.

Figure 11: VRPG: intrusion ranking from `gg_outliers(top_n = 15)`. Per-find noise-component posterior, sorted; the dashed line marks the 0.5 threshold. Unlike a rescaled composite, the posterior is an absolute probability and is not forced to span the full $[0, 1]$ range.

Figure 12: VRPG: mean entropy per US polygon (gg_map, layer = 'entropy'). Bright zones flag US with mixed-phase finds (potential palimpsests).

Figure 13: VRPG: mean ESE per US polygon (gg_map, layer = 'energy'). Bright zones indicate US with high local stratigraphic disruption.

Figure 14: VRPG: mean intrusion probability per US polygon (`gg_map`, layer = 'intrusion'). Highlights US containing potentially redeposited or out-of-context finds.

810 10 Data and code availability

811 The `palimpsestr` package (version 0.24.0 used in this paper) is publicly available at
 812 <https://github.com/enzococca/palimpsestr> under the MIT licence and permanently
 813 archived on Zenodo with concept DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19881542>. The
 814 `villa_romana` dataset, derived from the Poggio Gramignano excavation, is bundled with
 815 the package. The case-study figures were produced with the reproducibility script avail-
 816 able in the repository (`docs/regen_casestudy_v017.R`); the SEF model is unchanged
 817 since version 0.17.1, so they reproduce identically under 0.24.0. From version 0.20.0,
 818 `read_pyarchinit()` ingests `pyArchInit` databases directly, and a set of QGIS Processing
 819 algorithms with a self-installing `pyArchInit` tab runs the full pipeline — fitting, intrusion
 820 detection, and a narrated PDF/DOCX report (`export_sef_report()`) — from within
 821 QGIS (`qgis/` folder).

822 **11 Author contributions**

823 E.C. designed and implemented the `palimpsestr` package, the Stratigraphic Entangle-
824 ment Field framework, and the Shiny dashboard, and wrote the manuscript. R.M. directed
825 the archaeological excavations at Poggio Gramignano (Lugnano in Teverina), provided
826 the dataset and the taphonomic scores per stratigraphic unit, validated the model output
827 against on-site stratigraphic interpretation, and contributed to the discussion of method-
828 ological limitations and feature-space improvements. M.C. provided in-depth methodolog-
829 ical supervision throughout the development of the framework, contributed to the formu-
830 lation of the archaeological interpretation of the diagnostics (the redeposition score, the
831 unit-level palimpsest measure, and the type-longevity outlook), highlighted the implicit as-
832 sumption of horizontal stratigraphy, introduced the distinction between *older-than-context*
833 (residual) and *younger-than-context* (latent feature) intrusions in the roadmap, and identi-
834 fied the future case study on dendrochronologically dated pile-dwellings as the appropriate
835 validation context.

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845 **14 Conflict of interest**

846 The authors declare no conflict of interest relating to the content of this article.

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